

THE POTENTIAL OF HEALTH TOURISM DEVELOPMENT FOR INCOME AND A SUSTAINABLE ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT FOR ENTREPRENEUR AND COMMUNITY AFTER CORONAVIRUS 2019 OUTBREAK AT RANONG PROVINCE

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Abstract

Background- College of Allied Health Sciences, it's one of the educational institutions that provide teaching and learning in Medical and Public Health Sciences. The one part of responsibility educated institution with a mission to develop local foundations to achieve sustainability in various areas related to the economy, livelihood and sustainability of the community. Ranong Province is one of the administrative areas of the Suan Sunandha Rajabhat University. So, the researcher prepared a research project proposal. "The Potential of Health Tourism Development for Income and a Sustainable Administration and Management for Entrepreneur and Community after Coronavirus 2019 Outbreak at Ranong Province" (Department of Mental Health, 2020) with measurable expectation and the duration of the research results. Ranong province had a health-creative tourism destination, entrepreneurs and communities have sustainable incomes that were not a burden to the country. The goal has been set by 2024 and will help people in this area to earn better sustainable income. **Objective** - This research aimed to 1) to create a new way of product packaging schemes to increase access to local products; 2) to generate post-COVID-19 income from local products using the 4T marketing strategy. **Methods** - The target group was 30 persons collected by simple random sampling with the action research. The research referred to a quantitative technique that analysed data using descriptive statistics, manipulate variable analysis and inferential statistics. **Results** - The results showed that satisfaction with the packaging style of Ranong Provincial Community at the highest level, in terms of packaging, they had the highest level of satisfaction of the first activity. And, the result of the second activity about the consumer's tangible and touchable, transparent Pricing, timely and truth of marketing communication showed that the community had in a moderate level of overall satisfaction with the 4T marketing strategy where the tangible and touchable of consumers have the highest level of satisfaction. **Conclusion** - Findings in this research method to organize activities to engage with local entrepreneurs and community in developing the potential of health tourism destinations. (Bailey, 1987). It is to reinforce tourism with stories that entrepreneurs and community were involved in the operation. Create health-related products for tourists and connecting relationships together. This creates a dimension in creating stories where the knowledge from the local wisdom of the community really takes place in conservation and extending self-sustainability. Besides, to create the unique packaging development, such as the packaging of curry powder products, Baegu leaves cereal cookies product sticker, of Baegu and Pandan tea packaging, Butterfly pea tea, Lemongrass, Pandan and Baegu leaves, and Pandan leaves tea. Then, generated income from the acquisition of new packaging, such as the packaging of curry powder products, and tea leaves. So, there is a wider variety of sales through word of mouth. For example, from health tourists who want products from the community? Distribution of local community products and increased access to quality products

Keywords: Packaging Development, Management, Health Tourism, Ranong Province.

Background

The concept of The Potential of Health Tourism Development for Income and a Sustainable Administration and Management for Entrepreneur and Community after Coronavirus 2019 Outbreak at Ranong Province. Due to develop local foundations to achieve sustainability in various areas related to the economy, livelihood and sustainability of the community. (Goeldner & Ritchie, 2006). The Impact of the Covid-19 Pandemic Crisis (Department of Medicine, 2021) that happened adjusting the guidelines for developing and management (Hellriegel, Slocum, Jackson, 2005) with a new country to lead the country to escape from the Covid-19 crisis and ready for any changes or other crises that may arise in the future as well as responding to a new way of life. Therefore, Thailand's adaptation approach to step into "New life" or "New Normal" effectively and can overcome this crisis well. The development of secondary cities to support the national strategy after the outbreak of the coronavirus 2019 (Chobpradit, S, 2020) was something that everyone must do together. Ranong Province was one of the administrative areas of the university. So, the researcher prepared a research for this project with measurable expected results with modern market and connect to health-creative tourism destination, entrepreneurs and community have sustainable incomes that were not a burden to the country. (Jefkins, 1992). The goal has been set by 2024 and will help people in the area to earn better sustainable creative health tourism.

Methodology

This research employed the quantitative technique and action research with two activities, 1) creating packaging schemes for new ways of products to increase access to local products, and 2) generating post-COVID-19 income from local products using a 4T marketing strategy. The target group was 30 persons collected by simple random sampling with action research, to use a quantitative technique that analysed data using descriptive statistics, manipulate variable analysis and inferential statistics. Then, to follow research conceptual framework, as picture 1

Picture 1 Conceptual Framework

Source: Phannee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Data analysis

The research analyzed demographic characteristics by the descriptive statistics such as percentage, mean and standard deviation to build the manipulate variable activities, to focus the participation of local people in packaging designed stories and impact with customer satisfaction.

Results

The findings indicated that most of the research respondents were female (83%) to be an officer (45.90 %) aged between 46 – 99 years old (60 %). Most of them had an educational background in high school and vocational education (66 %) with occupation in own business (80 %) as a table 1 as following;

Table 1: Personal background (n = 30)

List	Quantity	%
Gender		
Male	5	17
Female	25	83
Age		
18 – 30 years	2	6
31 – 45 years	5	17
46 – 59 years	18	60
60+ years	5	17
Edcation		
Primary school	2	7
Secondary	20	66
Education/Vocational	8	27
Bachelor's degree	-	-
Postgraduate		
Occupation		
Student	-	-
employee	-	-
Trading/Personal	24	80
business	3	10
Government officer	3	10
Farming/Gardening	-	-
Other		

Activities 1

Activity 1 to create a new packaging as the following processes:

- 1) Packaging designed by surveyed theirs used to contain food for tourism.
- 2) Studied type of the packaging for dry and wet goods packing based on the guidelines to meet the needs of the target group.

- 3) A survey of the needs and preferences of packaging replacements that is suitable for local products.
- 4) Organized training on making packaging for entrepreneurs and the community with sample 30 people.
- 5) Product designed summary.

Picture 2: Activity 1

Source: Phannee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Result Activities 1

Normally, a previous design of packaging format used to pack food for consumption is mostly plastic bags. Because it was easy to sell, especially, according to tourist attractions. An appearance of the logo attached was a paper sticker and flashy colored plastic envelopes. So, after had development for all packaging, they were attracted and interested, as the picture 3 and table 2 for satisfaction analysis.

Picture 3: Previous design

Source: Phannee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Then, the designed packaging for community performed as local wisdom together with them was released in new way as picture 4 and 5.

Picture 4: new packaging design for tea and curry

Source: Phanee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Picture 5: new sticker design for cooky and curry

Source: Phanee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Picture 6: New packaging design for tea, cooky and curry

Source: Phanee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Next, to survey the satisfaction with the packaging style about usage, product protection, and packing, the data at the table 2 as the following below;

Table 2: Satisfaction with the packaging style (n = 30)

Packaging Style	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (S.D)	Result
1. Usage	4.27	0.290	Most
1.1 Ability to protect internal products	4.97	.320	The most
1.2 Easy to open and convenient to store the rest of the product	4.47	.681	Most
1.3 Can see the product inside the package	4.60	.675	The most
1.4 The packaging style is modern.	4.07	.640	Most
2. Product protection	4.54	0.493	Most
2.1 Can prevent contact with water humidity and air	4.73	0.521	The most
2.2 The material used can prevent contact with water, moisture and air.	4.57	0.626	The most
2.3 It can prevent the impact that damages the product.	4.57	0.626	The most
2.4 Can be completely sealed	4.43	0.627	Most
2.5 The packaging is suitable for the product.	4.40	0.621	Most
3. Packing	4.55	0.497	The most
3.1 Packed in the right amount Convenient to carry, carry and store	4.47	.629	Most
3.2 Packaging can be applied to other products.	4.63	.615	The most

Table 2 showed that the satisfaction with the packaging style of the community enterprise group in Ranong province at the highest level. Packaging refers to the material used to wrap products or things to make them attractive or to help protect the product and graphics refer to images or text and patterns that appear on the packaging for use. In terms of product protection, packaging is at a high level. With the highest level of satisfaction in packing.

Then, the result of the second activity in terms of the consumer's sense of touch pricing timeliness and marketing communication showed that the community had a moderate level of overall satisfaction with the 4T marketing strategy where tangible and touchable solution of consumers have the highest level of satisfaction.

Activities 2

Activities 2 to generating Post-Covid-19 income from local products using a 4T marketing strategy". As following;

- 1) To surveyed local Market and market demand to obtain marketing information.
- 2) Organize training on "4T Marketing Strategy" for entrepreneurs and communities With target of 30 people.
- 3) To assess the satisfaction of the 4T marketing strategy as a tool to study the use of marketing.

Picture 7: Activity 2

Source: Phannee Rojanabenjakun (2565)

Result Activities 2

To assess the satisfaction about the tangible and touchable solution, timely, transparent pricing and truth of marketing communication from customer. The results revealed that the community had a moderate level of overall satisfaction with the 4T marketing strategy where the tangible and touchable consumers and timely satisfaction at a high level, transparent pricing and truth of marketing communication at a high level where the sense of touchable solution of consumers have the highest level.

Then, the result about 4T strategic training which concerned the ability to serve the local products in the local market. The data of the satisfaction of training were as following;

Table 3: Satisfaction with the 4 T strategy (n = 30)

Marketing Strategy 4 T of Products	Mean (\bar{x})	Standard Deviation (S.D)	Result
1. Tangible and Touchable Solution	4.54	0.173	The most
1.1 Representing local identity as a selling point	4.57	0.504	The most
1.2 Can create memories and impressive	4.53	0.571	The most
1.3 Clearly conveys the benefits of the product.	4.50	0.682	Most
1.4 Beautiful, eye-catching design to make consumers interested	4.40	0.770	The most
2. Transparent Pricing	3.76	0.173	Most
2.1 Prices are clearly displayed.	4.03	0.183	The most
2.2 Pricing is fair to consumers	3.20	0.407	Most
2.3 Before pricing there is a comparison with similar products.	4.03	0.183	The most
3. Timely	3.88	0.299	Most
3.1 Appropriate order queue.	4.03	0.556	Most
3.2 Safe delivery of goods	3.67	0.547	Most
3.2 Timely delivery appointments	3.80	0.610	Most
4. Truth of Marketing communication	3.88	0.194	Most
4.1 To appropriate communication of product quality.	3.80	0.484	Most
4.2 To provide product information is not exaggerated.	3.97	0.490	Most
4.3 To repeat purchases	3.77	0.568	Most

Table 3 As the result showed that the consumer's tangible and touchable solution, transparent pricing, timely and truth marketing communication after survey revealed that the community had a moderate level of overall satisfaction with the 4T marketing strategy where the tangible consumers and timely satisfaction at a high level, transparent pricing and truth of marketing communication at a high level where the sense of touch of consumers have the highest level respectively.

Discussion

The objective of “The Potential of Health Tourism Development for Income and a Sustainable Administration and Management for Entrepreneur and Community after Coronavirus 2019 Outbreak at Ranong Province” were to 1) to create a new way of product packaging schemes to increase access to local products and 2) to generate post-COVID-19 income from local products using the 4T marketing strategy. (Department of Mental Health, 2564). This research was conducted according to research methodology quantitative research model is divided into 2 activities as follows: Activity 1 was to “Creating new packaging formats for products in a new way to increase access to local products” and activity 2 was to “Monetization after COVID-19 from local products using 4T marketing strategy” (Chusri, W and Lalitsasiwimol, W, 2020).

The research found that most of the packaging formats used in food packaging for consumption were plastic bags. Because it was easy to sell, consistent with (Phonngam, P, (2008), who had studied the developing potential and standards of OTOP products: a case study in local weaving groups, found that packaging development was important and they required to develop weaving for unique local fabric pattern. Furthermore, they help need to get a beautiful packaging to add value and attract customers. So, Entrepreneurs were more interested in developing a positive approach to expand in various areas related to packaging development. Besides, consistent with Chusri, W and Lalitsasiwimol, W, (2020) who said that the competitiveness analysis of the health tourism market of Thailand found that had been growing in a positive direction. In addition, in terms of packaging development also consistent with Wiriyawit, N (2016) which concerned in packaging development and public relations media for herbal cosmetic products, case study: Community, Minburi District, Bangkok, found that the packaging and labels were not prominent and attract to consumers. (Apiratnanusorn, S and Jinapak, K, 2013)

In Ranong Province, the appearance of the logo attached was a paper sticker and flashy colored plastic envelopes for dry and wet goods packaging. Then, the researcher studied for all environment and did survey the need and satisfaction to change the packaging format that was suitable for local products. The sample group was satisfied with the packaging style at the highest level. Currently, the community understands the packaging designed which concerned in graphics, images, text and patterns that appeared on the functional packaging. In terms of product protection, packaging, the satisfaction was at a high level. (Soiraya, B, et al., 2011). So, this was to increase access to local products.

About the Activity 2, Post-Covid 19 income from local products using 4T marketing strategy, the researchers created a process for market survey and market demand to get marketing

information by provided training found that "4T Marketing Strategy" for entrepreneurs and communities in trading business about were in high level of satisfaction. Whereas, the tangible and touchable solution was in the highest level. So, from the research had confidence that the customer had more knowledge and trust products or services from received marketing information. (Patornthanakul, E 2020).

Conclusion

The benefit of Activity 1 was to get the new packaging design that meets the requirement which did together with entrepreneur and community, it was found that the sample group chose design as the local wisdom. Besides, the design is modern Can be sold as a souvenir, knowledge of packaging and logo selection to suit locality and identity to achieve satisfaction and sustainability after the outbreak of the coronavirus 2019 in order to create income in Ranong province. About, training on making packaging for entrepreneurs and communities participants had a proper understanding of the design process. After the operation, it was found that the satisfaction with the packaging style of the community in Ranong province at the highest level.

The benefit of Activity 2 was to know about market survey and found the market demand in order to obtain marketing information, it was found that during the 2 years of the 2019 coronavirus epidemic, there would be very few people's travel, resulting in sluggish trading problems Entrepreneurs found ways to improve their products to meet the trade in many forms, especially, to do online sale. Therefore, to modernize the products attract consumer demand and the key was to be able to generate income. The research that provides training in packaging and 4T which answer the question of doing this research. About the Activity 2 found that entrepreneurs and community had more idea and understanding of how to improve products and services of 4T which followed tangible and touchable solution, transparent pricing, timely and truth of marketing communication.

Limitation

This research only studied of The Potential of Health Tourism Development for Income and a Sustainable Administration and Management for Entrepreneur and Community after Coronavirus 2019 Outbreak at Ranong Province. Should have studied more for standardize of products which concern of training people. (Fayol, 1925).

Declaration of Conflicting Interest

The author's declare no conflict of Interest.

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